

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE VESTIBULAR SYSTEM AND BODY BALANCE IN ADULTS (PART I): FALLS AND THEIR CONSEQUENCES IN THE ELDERLY

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These monthly bulletins aim to present information on different topics in the area of Health Education in a clear and accessible way.

Previous bulletins have dealt with the vestibular system and body balance in the pediatric population. We strongly recommend reading these, and they are listed in the references at the end.

This bulletin, however, focuses on another aspect which presents a serious problem for some adults and the elderly in particular – that is, the risk of falls.

VESTIBULAR SYSTEM: THE MAESTRO OF BODY BALANCE

The vestibular system is located at the back of the inner ear and is connected to the visual system, postural muscles, cerebellum, and brain.

The vestibular system is composed of three semicircular canals and two otolithic organs: saccule and utricle. Each semicircular canal and each otolithic organ are filled with fluid and contain a sensory receptor with tiny hair cells.

When the head is moved, the liquid moves and the hair cells bend, which triggers a nerve impulse that is sent to the brain.

The information from the vestibular system is processed in the brain and then sent to other organs that need it, such as the eyes, joints, or muscles. This allows us to maintain balance and know what position our body is in.

The semicircular canals detect the direction in which the head moves and the otolithic organs detect changes in the velocity of straight-line linear movements (forward, backward, or sideways, as in a car accelerating, or up and down, as in an elevator).

Inner ear

FALLS OF THE ELDERLY: A CHALLENGE FOR PUBLIC HEALTH

Falls represent a growing public health challenge, especially among the elderly. In the United States, alarming statistics reveal that about 30% of individuals aged 65 and over suffer at least one fall annually. This prevalence increases significantly with advancing age, reaching the 50% mark in those over 85 years of age.

In Europe, the direct consequences of falls are responsible for more than 1% of health costs.

It is important to look more deeply at this phenomenon, considering not only its frequency, but also its consequences. Falls in the elderly can result in fractures, head trauma, hospitalization, and, in more serious cases, even death. In addition, the fear of falling can lead to reduced mobility and social isolation, compromising quality of life and independence.

But what is the relationship between public health and falls in the elderly? Falls can lead to large public spending in the health sector, since the body and bones of the elderly are fragile, and a fall can trigger a series of rehabilitation expenses.

FACTORS THAT CONTRIBUTE TO INCREASED RISK OF FALLS IN OLDER PEOPLE

The factors can be considered under four categories.

Physiological decline: loss of muscle mass, decreased strength and balance, as well as changes in vision and proprioception, are part of the aging process and increase vulnerability to falls.

Chronic disease: Conditions such as heart disease, diabetes, Parkinson's, and Alzheimer's can affect mobility, balance, and cognition, increasing the risk of falls.

Use of medications: polypharmacy, especially the use of medications that cause drowsiness or postural hypotension, increases the likelihood of falls.

Environmental factors: unsafe environments, with inadequate lighting, slippery floors, loose carpets, and lack of handrails represent an additional risk for falls.

AGING AND PHYSIOLOGICAL DECLINE

Changes in body balance

Body balance is the result of a complex interaction between the sensory systems (visual, vestibular, and proprioceptive) and the musculoskeletal system.

The number of hair cells in the vestibular system gradually decrease from birth. Researchers have reported a decrease of about 6% per decade of life. At the same time, there is a decrease in the density of other sensory structures, the saccule and the utricle.

Although there is a constant decline in the number of hair cells with age, declines of the vestibular nerve and central nervous system begin around adulthood and then accelerates with age.

Associated with all these factors, there is a sensorimotor effect resulting from the way information is sent by each of these systems to the Central Nervous System (CNS) for processing. The aging process affects all systems and organs and this includes the vestibular system.

Vertigo

The etiology of vertigo is multifactorial and its symptoms are very common in the elderly population. The elderly depend strongly on somatosensory stimuli for body control.

Decrease in mechanoreceptors

Mechanoreceptors are specialized sensory cells, responsible for detecting mechanical stimuli such as pressure, vibration, and stretching.

In the feet, they play a crucial role in proprioception, which is the perception of the body's position and movement in space. With advancing age, the number of these receptors decreases, compromising the ability of the central nervous system to receive accurate information about the position of the feet and the distribution of body weight. This makes it difficult to maintain balance, especially in challenging situations such as walking on an uneven surface or making rapid changes of direction.

It is not uncommon for the elderly to have a decrease in plantar sensitivity, which can cause several problems in postural adjustments, whether as reflexes or planned actions. Impairments here limit the reactions possible by the Central Nervous System.

Changes in the urinary system

Medical conditions that lead to the urgent need to have a bowel movement as well as urinary incontinence, can significantly increase the risk of falls. The rush to get to the bathroom, often associated with difficulty controlling the sphincter, can compromise gait and balance, especially in individuals with reduced mobility or having other underlying health conditions.

Degenerative Diseases and Dementia

In the elderly, degenerative diseases are often associated with vestibular disorders, producing dizziness and/or gait instability. Gait deterioration under dual-task demands is typical, with cortical or subcortical involvement. The interaction between balance and cognition becomes more frequent when dementia is developing. Thus, the presence of impaired gait may be a sign of imminent dementia or degeneration.

WHAT ARE THE EFFECTS OF FALLING ON THE LIVES OF THE ELDERLY?

Falls in the elderly can have serious consequences and severely affect quality of life.

- After a fall, the fear of repeating it can lead to self-limitation, causing individuals to reduce their physical and social activities;
- The fear of falling can be associated with feelings of anxiety, depression, and social isolation, negatively impacting the quality of life and psychological well-being;
- Decrease in mobility and social participation can result in loss of muscle mass, reduced strength and balance, as well as the possibility of new falls;
- Loss of confidence in one's ability to move around safely can lead to dependence on others to perform everyday activities, restricting autonomy and independence;
- Extra expense for medical treatments;

In view of these scenarios, it is imperative to develop effective prevention and intervention strategies. These include health promotion, education about the risks of falls, adapting the home environment, and optimizing the treatment of any chronic diseases.

WHAT MEASURES CAN BE USED TO PREVENT FALLS?

Fall prevention is a crucial aspect of promoting health and wellness, especially for those with medical conditions which increase risk. Below are some effective preventive measures.

Medical condition management

It is important that people with urinary incontinence or other conditions that cause urinary urgency receive appropriate medical treatment to manage symptoms and reduce the risk of falls.

Muscle strengthening and balance

Muscle-strengthening exercises, especially for the lower limbs, and activities that promote balance, such as Tai Chi and Yoga, can help prevent falls.

Medication review

It is important to regularly review medications with a doctor or pharmacist to identify those that may increase the risk of falls. If required, alternatives can be investigated.

Adapting the environment

Lighting rooms well, removing obstacles, installing grab bars in bathrooms and hallways, using non-slip mats, and ensuring that the floors are in good condition are all important measures to make the home safer.

Use of assistive devices

Walking sticks, walkers, and other assistive devices can provide support and increase stability while walking, reducing the risk of falls.

Remember that fall prevention is an ongoing effort and requires the collaboration of health professionals, family members, and the individual themselves. By taking appropriate preventive measures, it is possible to significantly reduce the risk of falls and promote a safer and more independent life.

SUPPORT MATERIALS FOR THE ELDERLY

Fortunately, there are good materials that can provide guidance to family members and caregivers. **Some are listed below.**

1. The World Health Organization website (**WHO | Falls** - About Falls) offers information about the problem, including statistics, causes, and prevention strategies.
2. The U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (**Fall Prevention | CDC**) has a section dedicated to fall prevention, with tips and resources for seniors and healthcare professionals.
3. The NCOA (**National Council on Aging (NCOA) | Fall Prevention**) is an American organization offering programs and resources to help seniors prevent falls.

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